

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

THE PROBLEMS OF SHAPING THE ECOSPACE OF THE INFOCOMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY SYSTEM

Sergey S. Mishuk

*Doctor of Philosophy, Associate Professor
Belarusian Scientific Research Institute of Documentation and Archival affairs,
Department of Archives and Records Management
Ministry of Justice, Republic of Belarus
Deputy Director for Research*

Abstract

The functioning of the system of info-communication technologies in modern conditions has led to the emergence of a special virtual sphere, which has gradually acquired global dimensions and formed a truly civilisation-wide "reasonable shell". At present, the internal regularities of its functioning are beginning to manifest themselves quite prominently, and an internal eco-space of the info-communication technologies system is being formed, with data-centres acting as one of its elements.

Keywords: information society, noosphere, infocommunication technologies, paradigmatic factor, ecological space, data-centres.

The functioning of the system of info-communication technologies in modern conditions has led to the emergence of a special virtual sphere, which has gradually acquired global proportions and formed a truly all-civilisational "reasonable shell", the necessity and regularity of the emergence of which was brilliantly foreseen by V.I. Vernadsky[1].

This virtual sphere has reached such a level that its own laws of functioning and development are beginning to appear. One of such laws is, in our opinion, a specific reflection of already existing components of the real human civilisation in the structure of virtual reality.

Virtual reality as if repeats social reality. Of course, this repetition is not literal, but taking into account the specifics of the virtual sphere itself. Nevertheless, in fact, there is a kind of "doubling" of the already existing human society, its structural components and the processes taking place in them. In the virtual sphere, analogues of economic, social, political and spiritual spheres of real public life have already appeared. Some of them are sufficiently developed, others are just being formed. But the very fact of existence and development of these processes is, in our opinion, obvious for the beginning of the XXI century.

However, at present, the development of the information and communication technologies system in the general civilisational context is not limited to these processes. The ICT system is beginning to gradually go beyond its own limits. Initially, it was created and began to develop in the existing conditions already existing in various spheres of social life. However, at the present stage, algorithms seem to go beyond the purely technical component, beyond machines [2]. They no longer simply set certain norms and procedures of functioning, in accordance with which the nature of the work of material systems changes. They begin to actively transform physical reality itself. Built on the basis of micro-objects and micro-processes, the system of information and communication technologies begins to change the

world of macro-objects and macro-processes. It already requires external conditions for its existence that would correspond to its own nature. Just as human society as a whole transforms the nature surrounding it, creates a special so-called "second nature" in the process of its existence that meets its needs, the system of info-communication technologies is already beginning to form its own "habitat". It is obvious that the structure, properties and ways of existence of the latter follow from the structure and properties of the ICT sphere itself. This new component of man's "second nature" reflects and manifests the essential properties of the system of info-communication technologies, which, in its turn, is a natural and necessary continuation of the universal planetary sphere of mind.

In the totality of these processes, new aspects of the paradigmatic importance of information and communication technologies for modern society are manifested. The characteristics of the new structural elements of the "second nature" should already correspond exactly to the needs of effective functioning of the ICT system components. In fact, a special "ecological space" with specific parameters is emerging. And already now we can conclude that the purposeful formation of the above-mentioned space in the near future will turn into an essential element of the development of human society as a whole, which will require the solution of a whole complex of environmental, economic, social, technical, socio-psychological and other problems. Moreover, the progressive development of mankind will largely depend on their timely and successful resolution.

The requirements for the structure, characteristics and ways of functioning of the information and communication technology ecospace need to be most clearly manifested in the study of objects originally created for the ICT system, rather than taken from other components of human society and adapted for its purposes. Moreover, the size of these objects should also

be significant, so that potential problems in their creation and functioning become more apparent.

From our point of view, DATA-centres, or data processing centres (DPCs), are a rather illustrative example of this type of ICT structure objects. The emergence of these elements of the information and communication technology system once again confirms the general pattern of "doubling" of human society structures, manifested in the development of the virtual sphere. These centres are analogues of such a necessary component of a developed society as archives.

We would also like to note that this process clearly demonstrates another regularity in the development of the ICT system - very often the achievement of goals that are declared when creating its elements leads to directly opposite results. Thus, the active introduction of personal computers in the 90s of the XX century had as one of its arguments a supposed sharp decrease in the volume of document circulation, a fundamental reduction in the number of paper documents. In reality, the number of papers increased by orders of magnitude; the volume of traditional archives increased in the same proportion; digitisation of existing paper documents was required, etc. And now the need to create centres for storing digital, electronic documents, as well as for centralised processing of huge volumes of information, has become very acute.

Data centres seem to be necessary elements of the structure of info-communication technologies. They should have naturally emerged as certain nodes of the virtual space being formed. And at the level of data-centres the specific features of the ICT ecological space are already sufficiently manifested. Before that, at other levels of organisation, in other forms and ways of building their own space of the info-communication technologies system, its essential characteristics were also present, but they were manifested in a "hidden", undeveloped form. They seemed to continue the already existing structures of the "second nature", to be built into it, without introducing serious changes. Rather, purely quantitative transformations were present there.

At the level of data-centres, these special quantitative changes move to a new qualitative state - they begin to appear quite brightly and clearly; they become sufficiently developed and formalized for comprehensive analysis. On this basis, it becomes possible to better understand those elements that were already present at earlier stages of info-communication technology system formation. Therefore, it is from the level of data centres that it becomes possible to fully consider the main directions and regularities of forming one's own "ecological space" (one's own "ecological environment") of the information and communication technologies system.

Information processing centres form fundamentally important structural elements of their own space of info-communication technologies with specific ecological characteristics [3]. Moreover, these centres, in addition to being included in the processes of virtual reality functioning, represent elements of the physical-object world, the macro-world. They interact with the

already existing elements of civilisation; they are embedded in the "second nature", but do not coincide with it completely.

These centres have in this sense a twofold nature.

On the one hand, they are new elements of the "second nature", new structural components of the inorganic body of human civilisation.

On the other hand, they are "nodes" forming and structuring their own ICT spaces. They manifest new substantial aspects of the system of information and communication technologies as a necessary element of the noosphere. Hence, there are two directions of their development, two groups of properties and characteristics required to fulfil their tasks.

The first direction is associated with the need to interact with the external environment, with the already formed "second nature".

The second one is conditioned by the tasks of forming the internal ecospace, arising from the regularities of functioning of the ICT system itself.

Let us analyse the above-mentioned directions.

At a closer look, the first direction breaks down into two components.

Firstly, data centres should meet the requirements already formed within the framework of the "second nature" to the objects of such purpose. First of all, security and guarantees of stability of operation of these elements of ICT space should be provided, taking into account both purely natural and anthropogenic factors. Let us try to briefly list some of them: ensuring stability and protection from natural forces; sufficient protection from disasters; reliable protection from unauthorised intrusion, from terrorist acts; ensuring their own ecological purity, absence of harmful emissions of various kinds, etc...

Secondly, the necessary external infrastructural conditions should be provided to ensure the sustainable functioning of such facilities.

First of all, data centres require special energy supply. For example, in the USA already in 2010 the cost of electricity consumed annually by such centres exceeded the cost of purchased and installed equipment. In order to meet the electricity demand for the number of data centres required for the normal development of the ICT system in the United States, ten medium-sized power plants need to be put into operation each year. A data centre would actually require a separate power plant to operate. As a result, the problems of power supply (both permanent and backup) become a major issue. Accordingly, the problem of reducing power consumption by such centres, ensuring energy efficiency in all components of such system objects - at the level of engineering infrastructure, at the level of servers in general and their element base, data transmission lines, etc. - becomes extremely acute.

It should be noted that, despite the apparent priority, reducing energy consumption and improving energy efficiency cannot be an end in itself. Such nodes of info-communication technologies require a systematic approach to ensure their functioning. And the reverse side of high energy consumption is the necessity to dissipate heat generated in the process of information

and communication equipment operation. These processes have a direct interdependence - the more electricity the equipment consumes, the more heat is generated and, consequently, the more energy is required for cooling.

The second direction of development of these components of the info-communication technologies system is realised in the processes of forming its own ecological space, the parameters of which should ensure the sustainability and efficiency of the ICT system as a whole. Ecospace inside data centres should correspond to specific physical and chemical parameters, provide a certain microclimate, etc.

It should be noted that in the available literature the analysis of the conditions of functioning of such type of facilities is mainly limited to the above-mentioned aspects of the first direction of their development. In our opinion, this is not enough, because this approach does not take into account the specific essential properties of the information and communication technology system. It differs from the global systems previously created by man, as it is not only techno-technological. Therefore, the processes of forming its ecospace will be much more complex.

The second direction in the development of the ecospace of the info-communication technologies system should include the problems related to the functioning conditions of both technical devices and the human being involved in the maintenance of these objects.

To the first group of problems can be attributed: the need to ensure an appropriate temperature regime; maintenance of a certain level of humidity; the need for a highly effective ventilation system; the ecological space of these facilities must be free of dust, otherwise the equipment quickly fails; in this ecological environment will inevitably arise specific biocomponents and others

All the above-mentioned factors will also affect people working inside such facilities. At least three directions of such impact are already clearly visible here.

Firstly, the impact on human physical health. It is necessary to take a whole set of measures, starting from protective clothing, special labour regime and finishing with special measures on rehabilitation of service personnel to ensure the possibility of normal work.

Secondly, the formed ecological environment of this type will have a constant impact on the mental state

of human employees with the whole complex of its parameters. As a result, unnoticeable for the external observer and the person himself can occur changes in the psyche, resulting in a decrease in attention, memory, etc.

Thirdly, in these structural components of the space of information and communication technologies there will be such a phenomenon as "electromagnetic smog", when a large concentration of electromagnetic fields and impulses come into resonance with both electromagnetic impulses of the human brain and with the electrical systems working inside it (for example, a pacemaker).

It should be emphasised that it is the latter two directions that represent, in our opinion, the greatest potential danger, as their initial manifestations are less noticeable, but the result of their influence is an imbalance of the whole human organism, as they affect the central nervous system. This seems to be quite natural. The system of information and communication technologies, as a necessary element of the noosphere, has the greatest impact, first of all, on those structures that contain the "noos" (mind) component.

Thus, the development of the system of info-communication technologies leads at the present stage to the emergence and formation of a special ecological space, which is required for its normal functioning. The process of emergence of elements of such a space gives rise to a number of problems related both to the existence of the inorganic body of human civilisation and the established global ecological balance, and to the life activity of man himself, the development of whose essential forces the system of info-communication technologies is.

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